

Estimation of bromide and sulphate in common table salt and high purity solar salt employing ion chromatographic technique (NM-10)

Babulal Rebary^{a*}, Meera Raichura^a, S. C. Upadhyay^b and Parimal Paul^{a*}

^aAnalytical Discipline & Centralized Instrument Facility, ^bSPEU Discipline,
CSIR-Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute, Bhavnagar-364 002, Gujarat, India

E-mail : babulal@csmcri.org, ppaul@csmcri.org Fax : 91-278-2567562

Abstract : The determination of bromide and sulphate present in table salt and high purity solar salt was accomplished by ion chromatography. Quantitative estimation of the anions in synthetic samples has been obtained and the interferences from different cations and anions have been studied. Total bromide/sulphate was determined without any treatment with silver cartridge for high chloride matrix removal. Quantitative analysis was feasible for bromide and sulphate concentrations ≥ 4 ; 10 ppm, respectively in salt. The method has been successfully applied to the determination of bromide and sulphate in the commercially available salts as well as in the high purity solar salt for industrial application.

Keywords : Bromide, sulphate, high purity solar salt, table salt, AS 11-HC, AS 11, ion chromatography-conductivity detection.

Introduction

In the course of the 20th century bromide has been introduced increasingly into the environment as a salt-mining waste and a degradation product of fumigants. The new role of bromide as a residue in food and water necessitated its broad toxicological evaluation¹⁻⁴, 1 mg/L is considered as the maximum permissible limit of bromide in drinking water. On the occurrence of high amounts in environmental samples, bromide represents a hazard to public health⁵. Brominated and iodinated compounds are produced during the disinfection of water by chlorine in the presence of bromide and iodide^{6,7}. Toxicological studies suggest that brominated and iodinated compounds may be more carcinogenic than chlorinated analogues⁸. There is no standard specification for bromide in table salt. Considering the chemical similarity of bromine to iodine, on the other hand, goitrogenic effects of bromide may be assumed. Long-term elevated dietary levels of bromide exert changes on the status of the thyroid gland, with eventual substitution of iodide by bromide during biosynthesis of thyroid hormones^{9,10}. Indeed, an enhanced bromide intake in the rat could markedly reduce iodide accumulation in the thyroid^{11,12}, as well as in the skin¹³. Bromine has a similar chemical and biological behaviour

as iodine. While this element could be an essential element, excessive bromide in the organism of experimental animals can influence their iodine metabolism by decreasing iodide accumulation. Thus, bromine intake must be checked and controlled when iodine intake is concerned^{14,15}. However, in year 2007 an outbreak of acute neurological disease was most likely due to bromide poisoning which occurred through ingestion of table salt contaminated with sodium bromide occurred in Cacucaco municipality, Luanda Province, Angola¹⁶. The World Health Organization has set a maximum acceptable bromide intake for humans at 1 mg/kg of body weight per day. In adult males, the bromine content in serum has been found to be 3.2–5.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, in urine 0.3–7.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and in hair 1.1–49.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ¹⁷. The world salt production has crossed 240 million ton per annum and more than 60% of the total salt produced is used for industrial applications, chlor-alkali and speciality chemical industries being the major consumers. The presence of sulphate, bromide and other trace element impurities may necessitate further purification of the harvested salt to make it suitable for its specific end use. Superior quality industrial grade salt with specified limits of calcium, magnesium, sulphate, bromide and other trace element is

preferred by these industries as the use of such salt reduces the brine purification cost and effluent generation.

Spectrophotometric¹⁸⁻²², volta metric²³, electrophoresis²⁴, ICP-MS²⁵, GC-MS²⁶, IC-ICP-MS²⁷ and CE-ICP-MS²⁸ methods have been reported for the determination of bromide in saline matrix. Ion chromatography has been traditionally used for determining bromate, other oxyhalides and halides using a carbonate eluent and suppressed conductivity detection²⁹⁻³². A hydroxide eluent has been found to have lower suppressed background conductivity³³. High levels of chloride affect the ion chromatography of bromide³⁴, and sulphate^{35,36}. Postcolumn reaction or conversion into a more detectable organic derivative are two ways used to overcome this problem for bromide³⁷. As per literature survey, all above mentioned methods have innate limitations as many of these required specific compounds, costly equipment, complex reactions, sample pre-treatment and derivatization reagents, e.g. *N,N*-dimethylaniline has variable stoichiometry when bromide is determined, phenylboronic acid-mercuric nitrate³⁸ is unsuitable when large excess of chloride is present. Interestingly we have not found much literature for sulphate quantification in table salt except two articles^{35,36}. We have found in this work that AS 11 HC Dionex column gives good separation for chloride, sulphate and bromide compared to the AS 11 Dionex column where separation for these anion was quite low. In our optimized strategy sulphate and bromide can be easily separated within 0.5% salt solution (NaCl matrix) without any pre-treatment.

Experimental

Equipment and IC conditions :

The DX500 system from Dionex (Sunnyvale, CA, USA) consisted of a GP50 gradient pump with vacuum degas option, an ED40 electrochemical detector, LC-25 liquid chromatography module, EO1 eluant organizer and rheodyne injection loop. PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) filters with pore size of 0.45 μm were obtained from Millipore India Pvt. Ltd. Separations were accomplished on a Dionex column, IonPac AS 11-HC (250 mm \times 4 mm i.d.), coupled with a guard column (50 mm \times 4 mm i.d.) of the same filling. The high-capacity AS 11-HC column allows the injection of more concentrated samples without column overloading or peak broadening, and pro-

vides improved separation over the AS 11 column for anions. 30 mM NaOH was employed as mobile phase and elution was carried out under isocratic condition at a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The injection loop volume was fixed at 10 μL and the sample run time was 10 min. The conductivity detector with suppressor ASRS 300 (4 mm) and external water mode was employed with 100 mA applied current.

Deionized water for the eluant preparation was degassed before use by flushing nitrogen for about 10 min. The plastic reservoir bottles (DX 500 1L bottles, Dionex) were closed and pressurized with pure nitrogen to 50 kPa. The system was interfaced, via proprietary network chromatographic software (PeakNet), to a personal computer for instrumentation control, data acquisition and processing (Dionex). For comparison study with AS 11 column we used 12 mM NaOH as eluant and flow rate was 1 mL/min. The injection loop volume was fixed at 10 μL and the sample run time was 10 min. The conductivity detector with suppressor ASRS 300 (4 mm) and external water mode was employed with 100 mA applied current.

Reagents and standards :

Commercial table salt samples were obtained from the local market. Deionized water of 18.2 M Ω -cm resistivity (Millipore system), ultrapure 50% NaOH (Sigma Aldrich), supra pure grade NaCl (Merck), ACS grade NaBr and Na₂SO₄ (Sigma Aldrich) were used as received. Stock solutions of NaBr (1.29 g/L) and Na₂SO₄ (1.48 g/L) were prepared in deionized water and the solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by appropriately diluting the stock solutions with deionized water. The NaOH eluant (30 mM) was prepared from 50% saturated solution (1.6 ml/L) and ultrasonicated for 10 min before use. For interference study the compounds used were sodium chloride, calcium chloride, magnesium chloride, potassium iodide, sodium fluoride, ferric chloride, potassium nitrate, cupric chloride, cobaltous chloride, nickel chloride and potassium iodate. These were all of analytical grade and purchased from Qualigens Fine Chemicals (Mumbai, India). Deionized water was used throughout. All solutions were filtered through 0.45- μm membrane filters before use.

Preparation of high purity solar salt :

Solar salt having $\text{SO}_4^{2-} = 0.28\%$ and $\text{Br}^- = 60$ ppm was produced as per the procedures available in literature. It was mixed with fresh sea brine having an initial density of $3 \text{ }^0\text{Be}'$. The brine was saturated with NaCl by dissolving the salt till the brine attained $25 \text{ }^0\text{Be}'$ density. The saturated brine ($25 \text{ }^0\text{Be}'$) so obtained was transferred to pre-crystallizer ponds and treated with flocculating agents like alum at a concentration of 25–75 ppm and was allowed to settle for 48 h. The saturated brine of $25 \text{ }^0\text{Be}'$ density was allowed to evaporate upto $27 \text{ }^0\text{Be}'$ and crystallized salt was harvested, heaped and washed with fresh water. The washed salt was subjected to solar drying and achieved high purity solar salt.

Determination of bromide and sulphate :

Calibration for bromide and sulphate within NaCl matrix :

The stock solution of NaBr and Na_2SO_4 was diluted to obtain concentrations in the range 0.02–1, 0.05–20 mg/L, respectively with 5 g/L NaCl matrix (200 fold dilutions) which translates to 4–200 ppm bromide and sulphate 10–4000 ppm in salt. These solutions were analysed on the ion chromatography system (the run time was 10 min) and a linear plot of peak area ($\mu\text{S min}$) versus concentration (mg/L) was generated using Peaknet software. The straight line had a slope of 4.45×10^{-2} , $7.75 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{S min mg}^{-1} \text{ L}^{-1}$, correlation coefficient were 0.9999, 0.9999 and RSD of 2.98%, 2.03% for bromide and sulphate, respectively. For both anion (bromide and sulphate) the concentration of 2 ppm in salt appeared to be the detection limit, albeit with substantial error in estimation. 0.5% (w/v) sample solutions were used for determination of total bromide and sulphate in table salt as well as in high purity solar salt.

Columns suitability :

The high-capacity AS 11-HC column allows separation of bromide and sulphate at retention time 5.1, 4.0 min, respectively using 30 mM NaOH mobile phase. The AS 11 columns allows the separation for bromide and sulphate at retention time 2.2, 2.4 min, respectively using 12 mM NaOH as mobile phase.

Determination of bromide and sulphate in table salt :

For the determination of total bromide and sulphate, a 5 g portion of homogenized table salt was dissolved in about 100 ml of deionised water, kept for 30 min and ultrasonicated for 10 min then 1 ml of this solution was diluted up to 10 ml giving 0.5% (w/v) final concentration which was used for analysis.

Results and discussion

The optimization strategy for NaCl matrix :

Table salts generally has the concentration of NaCl from 97 to 99%, since sulphate and bromide separates near to chloride, the higher chloride matrix may suppress the interested analytes. We have tried the different synthetic samples of 0.02 ppm of bromide and sulphate with 0.1%, 0.5% and 1% NaCl matrix and found the 0.5% as optimized as shown in Fig. 1, albeit with substantial error in sulphate (small hump of sulphate is appears even in supra pure NaCl). In case of 0.1% NaCl matrix the separation for bromide and sulphate was not up to acceptable range while in case of 1% NaCl matrix the analytical column was overloaded.

Separation of bromide and sulphate on AS 11-HC and AS 11 :

Comparative separation of 1 ppm of chloride, bromide and sulphate with and without 0.5% NaCl matrix on both columns were carried out and found that AS 11-HC gives good separation of above mentioned anions with and without NaCl matrix. In case of AS 11 column the separation for above mentioned anion was not enough even in matrix-less solution. Due to closer retention of sulphate and bromide, the higher chloride matrix has suppressed these anions. The observations are shown in Fig. 2.

Validation :

Laboratory samples of table salt were prepared by adding known amounts of bromide and sulphate to supra pure grade sodium chloride that was found to be free from any bromide and sulphate, and mixing thoroughly. Agreement between the standard additions to synthetic table salt, and the masses of bromide and sulphate found by the present method served to validate the new method (Table 1). The average recovery of spikes was in the

Fig. 1. Ion chromatogram of synthetic sample of (a) 1 mg L⁻¹ solution of Cl⁻, Br⁻ and SO₄²⁻ separated on column AS 11 without NaCl matrix (5 g/L), (b) 1 mg L⁻¹ solution of Br⁻ and SO₄²⁻ separated on column AS 11 with NaCl matrix (5 g/L), (c) 1 mg L⁻¹ solution of Cl⁻, Br⁻ and SO₄²⁻ separated on column AS 11-HC without NaCl matrix (5 g/L) and (d) 1 mg L⁻¹ solution of Br⁻ and SO₄²⁻ separated on column AS 11-HC with NaCl matrix (5 g/L).

Table 1. Determination of bromide and sulphate in the chloride matrix with column AS 11-HC (all results are the average of three determinations)

Laboratory made synthetic table salt samples ^a	Added Br ⁻ and SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	Bromide		Sulphate	
		Found (mg L ⁻¹)	Recovery (%) of spike	Found (mg L ⁻¹)	Recovery (%) of spike
1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.20	0.20	100	0.18	90.0
3	0.50	0.47	94.0	0.54	108
4	2.00	1.83	91.5	1.81	90.5
5	5.00	5.04	100	5.02	100

^aAll analyses were undertaken with 0.5% (w/v) aqueous salt solution.

Table 2. Bromide and sulphate estimation in commercial salt samples employing the ion chromatographic technique of the present work^a

Table salt brands Sample	IC-Conductivity detection with AS 11-HC column	
	Bromide (µg/g) ^b	Sulphate (%) ^c
A	56.40	0.23
B	121.24	0.39
C	181.54	0.18
D	205.40	0.18
D	101.22	0.44
D	18.2	0.27

^aAll analyses were undertaken with 0.5% (w/v) aqueous salt solution. Results provided are the average of three measurements. ^bValues shown are of bromide concentration in salt expressed in µg/g (ppm). ^cValues shown are of sulphate concentration in salt expressed in %.

Fig. 2. Ion chromatogram of synthetic sample of 0.02 mg L^{-1} solution of Br^- and SO_4^{2-} with NaCl matrix (1 g/L, 5 g/L and 10 g/L) separated on column AS 11-HC, (a) in full scale, (b) in expanded scale and (c) in bar diagram format showing 5 g/L NaCl matrix is optimized working back ground matrix.

Fig. 3. Ion chromatogram of one real table salt sample from market showing the bromide (r.t. 5.0 min) and sulphate (r.t. 3.9 min) peak.

Table 3. Interference of different ions in bromide and sulphate determination in 0.5% NaCl solution

Sl. no.	Ions	Form	Conc. of the ion (mgL ⁻¹)	Added Br ⁻ and SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	Conc. Found (mg L ⁻¹)	
					Bromide	Sulphate
1.	Ca ²⁺ , Co ²⁺	Chloride	50	1	0.99 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.17
2.	Fe ³⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺	Chloride	100	1	1.12 ± 0.15	1.05 ± 0.15
3.	I ⁻ , IO ₃ ⁻	Potassium	50	1	1.10 ± 0.11	1.02 ± 0.12
4.	F ⁻	Sodium	50	1	1.01 ± 0.08	1.13 ± 0.02
5.	NO ₃ ⁻	Potassium	5	1	0.87 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.01

range 91.5–100.0% for bromide, and 99.6% (range 90.0–108.0%) for sulphate.

Analysis of real samples :

The present method has been applied to six table salt samples procured from local suppliers and to high purity solar salts to determine bromide and sulphate. The results are given in Table 2. The sulphate content was found upto 0.4% which is well matching with product specification of salt given by different manufacturers.

Interferences :

The interference of a number of different ions has been studied by spiking the standards with known quantities of foreign substances and analyzing it by the present method. The anions selected for the study were I⁻, F⁻, NO₃⁻, IO₃⁻ and the cations selected were Ca²⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺. The studies were carried out with 0.5% (w/v) sodium chloride containing 1 mg/L of both anions (this is equivalent to table salt containing 200 µg/

g (ppm) bromide/sulphate which is dissolved in water to obtain 0.5% NaCl), and into which the “impurity” ions were added. It can be concluded that the above ions do not interfere with the ion chromatographic analysis in any significant way (Table 3).

Conclusion

The proposed method involving use of high capacity columns for separation of bromide and sulphate, in high salt matrix without any sample pre-treatment, and it avoids many inconveniences of other classical techniques. The optimized NaCl matrix is compatible for separation of bromide and sulphate for this column and gives precise and accurate results in long range.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. P. K. Ghosh and Dr. V. P. Mohandas for helpful discussion throughout the work. We are grateful to CSIR, New Delhi for generous support towards infrastructure and core competency development.

References

1. C. Frances, G. Hoizey, D. Lamiable, H. Millart and T. Trenque, *Clin. Toxicol.*, 2003, **41**, 181.
2. F. X. R. Van Leeuwen and B. Sangster, *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.*, 1987, **18**, 189.
3. M. Flury and A. Papritz, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1993, **22**, 747.
4. F. X. R. Van Leeuwen, R. Hanemaaijer and J. G. Loeber, *Arch. Toxicol.*, 1988, **12**, 93.
5. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Residues and Toxicity of Bromide, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 1983, **21**, 357.
6. G. Hua and D. A. Reckhow, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2006, **384**, 495.
7. G. Hua, D. A. Reckhow and J. Kim, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **40**, 3050.
8. M. J. Plewa, E. D. Wagner, S. D. Richardson, A. D. Thruston, Y. Woo and A. B. McKague, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2004, **38**, 4713.
9. F. X. R. van Leeuwen, E. M. den Tonkelaar and M. J. van Logten, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 1983, **21**, 383.
10. J. G. Loeber, M. A. M. Franken and F. X. R. van Leeuwen, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 1983, **21**, 391.
11. W. Buchberger, W. Holler and K. Winsauer, *J. Trace Elem. Electrolytes Health Dis.*, 1990, **4**, 25.
12. S. Pavelka, A. Babický, M. Vobecký and J. Lener, in : "Industrial Toxicology '99", ed. V. Romaněik, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, 1999, 224.
13. S. Pavelka, A. Babický, M. Vobecký and J. Lener, *Biol. Trace Elem. Res.*, 2001, **82**, 133.
14. S. Pavelka, A. Babický, J. Lener and M. Vobecký, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 2002, **40**, 1041.
15. S. Pavelka, *Physiol. Res.*, 2004, **53**, S81.
16. K. Gutschmidt, P. Haeffliger and T. Zilker, "Outbreak of Neurological Illness of Unknown Etiology in Cacuaço Municipality", Angola, World Health Organization, WRO Angola, AFRO, HQ, 2007.
17. R. E. Cuenca, W. J. Pories and J. Bray, *Biol. Trace Elem. Res.*, 1988, **16**, 151.
18. N. Pourreza and S. Rastegarzadeh, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2001, **56**, 724.
19. S. Adimurthy, V. R. K. S. Susarla, M. P. Reddy and G. Ramachandraiah, *Talanta*, 2005, **67**, 891.
20. K. Uraisin, D. Nacapricha, S. Lapanantnoppakhun, K. Grudpan and S. Motomizu, *Talanta*, 2005, **68**, 274.
21. K. Uraisin, T. Takayanagi, M. Oshima, D. Nacapricha and S. Motomizu, *Talanta*, 2006, **68**, 951.
22. M. P. Reddy, *Water, Air, Soil Pollut.*, 2009, **196**, 151.
23. H. I. I. Habib, N. A. H. Hassan and M. Stob, Proceedings of IUPAC International Congress on Analytical Sciences, 2001, (ICAS 2001), i1027.
24. W. Ding, M. J. Thornton and J. S. Fritz, *Electrophoresis*, 1998, **19**, 2133.
25. H. Kataoka, S. Tanaka, C. Konishi, Y. Okamoto, T. Fujiwara and K. Ito, *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.*, 2008, **22**, 1792.
26. K. Reddy-Noone, A. Jain and K. K. Verma, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2007, **1148**, 145.
27. Z. L. Chen, M. Megharaj and R. Naidu, *Chromatographia*, 2007, **65**, 115.
28. J. H. Chen, K. Wang and S. J. Jiang, *Electrophoresis*, 2007, **28**, 4227.
29. Method 300.0 : the Determination of Inorganic Anions in Water by Ion Chromatography, US Environmental Protection Agency, Cincinnati, OH, 1993.
30. W. Hu, P. R. Haddad, K. Hasebe, K. Tanaka, P. Tong and C. Khoo, *Anal. Chem.*, 1999, **71**, 1617.
31. E. Salhi and U. V. Gunten, *Wat. Res.*, 1999, **33**, 3239.
32. X. L. Jiang, L. W. Lim and T. Takeuchi, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2009, **393**, 387.
33. B. M. De Borba, J. S. Rohrer, C. A. Pohr and C. Saini, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2005, **1085**, 23.
34. P. L. Buldini, J. L. Sharma and S. Sharma, *Analyst*, 1994, **119**, 121.
35. A. S. Desai, V. D. Chougule, S. S. Patil and M. Sriram, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1999, **841**, 55.
36. S. D. Kumar, B. Maiti and P. K. Mathur, *Talanta*, 2001, **53**, 701.
37. A. Jain, A. Chaurasia, B. Sahasrabudhhey and K. K. Verma, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 1996, **746**, 31.
38. A. Sarafraz-Yazdi, M. Y. Khuhawar and P. C. Udèn, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1992, **594**, 395.

